

Modification of zeolite Na-X, sodalite and cancrinite in salt melts

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Abstract. The possibility of occlusion in melts of useful components of some of the most economically advantageous materials, obtained during zeolitization of fly ash – Na-X, sodalite and cancrinite, was investigated. A very high degree of occlusion of ZnCl₂ in zeolite Na-X was achieved along with complete exchange of Na extra-framework cations with Zn²⁺. By elution, it was proved that, in the interaction of zeolite Na-X with ZnCl₂ melt, occlusion takes place without destroying the zeolite aluminum-silicate framework. In a KNO₃ melt, in the narrowest pore structure – the sodalite structure, occlusion does not proceed, only ion exchange occurs. Through computer modeling, the ion exchange of both the charge-balancing cations and the synthetically incorporated cation-anion pairs has been proven. The interaction of cancrinite-SO₄ with a KNO₃ melt results in the formation of a material with an altered cationic composition and occluded KNO₃, which gradually comes out of the structure upon elution. The results obtained in the work can be a basis for the development of future applications of the modified minerals as materials with antibacterial properties (occluded ZnCl₂ in the structure of zeolite Na-X) and as slow-acting fertilizers or micro-fertilizers (occluded with KNO₃ cancrinite and sodalite forms).

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INTRODUCTION

Thermal power plants (TTPs) account for a large share of Bulgaria’s energy capacity. The work of TTPs generates a huge amount of fly and bottom ash, whose neutralization and secondary utilization are a challenge to the scientific community because, in Bulgaria, their application is not yet widely accepted. There are over 120 applications worldwide, some of which are widely used today. One of the most studied methods for their modification is their zeolitization. Through various synthesis methods, such as microwave hydrothermal treatment (Querol *et al.*, 1997; Inada *et al.*, 2005), ultrasonic hydro-

thermal synthesis (Musyoka *et al.*, 2011; Ojumu, 2016), molten salt method (Choi *et al.*, 2001), and hydrothermal treatment and alkaline synthesis (Shigemoto *et al.*, 1993; Berkgaut and Singer, 1996; Chang and Shih, 1998; Chang and Shih, 2000; Querol *et al.*, 2001, 2002; Molina and Poole, 2004; Ye and Yaping, 2008, Thuadaj *et al.*, 2012; Feng *et al.*, 2018; Stanimirova and Markov, 2019), various microporous aluminum-silicate minerals have been obtained – zeolites and feldspathoids.

Based on ion exchange and sorption properties of zeolitized fly ash (Querol *et al.*, 2002), synthetic zeolites (Ishiwata *et al.*, 2004; Ikemoto *et al.*, 2006; Wongthong *et al.*, 2007; Dickson *et al.*, 2014;

Komaty *et al.*, 2020;) and feldspathoids (Cisneros *et al.*, 2011), various applications have been described in the literature (Stein *et al.*, 1991, 1993; Linares *et al.*, 2005, 2008; Robben and Gesing, 2013; Dickson *et al.*, 2015a, b; Dip *et al.*, 2022). For example, through ion exchange of various cations, catalysts for petroleum chemistry and organic synthesis, microbicide substances for medicine, pharmacy and cosmetics have been obtained (Cerri *et al.*, 2004; Linares *et al.*, 2008). By secondary modification, sorbents of toxic anions (such as arsenate) and colloidal pollutants (Mn and other heavy metals) have been prepared. Through occlusion, a long-time emitting of useful substances into the environment has been assumed (Park and Komarneni, 1997; Park *et al.*, 2001).

The main objective of the present work is to study the process and products of occlusion of useful components in synthetic zeolites and feldspathoids, with potential possibilities for modification of zeolitized fly ash for medical and agricultural applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The phase composition of fly ash obtained from the operation of TPPs consists mainly of a glassy phase, amorphous carbon and small amounts of quartz, feldspars, mica and other minerals, depending on the solid fossil fuel source (Vassilev and Vassileva, 1996, 2007; Vassilev *et al.*, 2003; Stanimirova and Markov, 2019). Zeolites and feldspathoids are obtained at the expense of the glassy silicate phase, but the amorphous carbon and other crystalline phases remain in the system. In order to establish the full range of properties of zeolites and feldspathoids, they were synthesized in their pure form.

Synthetic forms of faujasite and various anionic forms of sodalite and cancrinite were obtained through an interaction of $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NaAlO_2 , with various additives (NaOH, NaCl,

NaNO_3 , and Na_2SO_4) under low-temperature hydrothermal conditions – 80 °C for 48 h. All syntheses were performed with analytical grade reagents. The specific conditions and quantities of reagents are presented in Table 1. The obtained products were filtered, washed to pH 8.5 of the wash water and finally dried at room temperature.

The occlusion experiments were carried out in a melt (temperature 324–350 °C) of ZnCl_2 (in zeolite Na-X) and KNO_3 (in sodalite and cancrinite). The experiments were carried out as 1 g of the starting materials were mixed with an equivalent amount or in excess (2 g) of the corresponding salt melt for 48 h. The resulting products, after cooling, were investigated and characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and FTIR spectroscopy.

To evaluate the degree of occlusion, elution of the occluded salts was carried out as occluded forms were washed with distilled water. The degree of washout was evaluated depending on the degree of recovery of the powder XRD pattern after elution.

The powder XRD patterns were recorded on a D8 Advance, Bruker diffractometer. Filtered $\text{Co-K}\alpha$ radiation was used in the range 2θ 4–80°, step 0.02° 2θ , and exposure time per step 1.5 s. The Diffrac.Eva software was used for qualitative and semi-quantitative phase composition determination. The PowderCell 2.2 software was used for simulation of powder XRD patterns based on structural data.

FTIR spectra in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} were recorded on an FTIR Bruker TENSOR 37 Spectrometer in KBr tablets, at a ratio of the investigated substance to KBr of 1:200.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The powder XRD patterns of all products show that the synthesized minerals are pure mono-mineral samples, without the presence of impurities

Table 1
Synthesis conditions and obtained products

	Starting solution	Si:Al	Additive	Product
1	10ml 2.7M $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 23ml 1M NaAlO_2	1:0.8	10 ml 3M NaOH	Zeolite Na-X
2	10ml 2.7M $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 23ml 1M NaAlO_2	1:0.8	10 ml 6M NaOH	Sodalite-OH
3	10ml 2.7M $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 23ml 1M NaAlO_2	1:0.8	10 ml 6M NaOH + 2 g NaCl	Sodalite-Cl
4	10ml 2.7M $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 23ml 1M NaAlO_2	1:0.8	10 ml 6M NaOH + 2 g NaNO_3	Cancrinite- NO_3
5	10ml 2.7M $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + 23ml 1M NaAlO_2	1:0.8	10 ml 6M NaOH + 2.5 g Na_2SO_4	Cancrinite- SO_4

(Fig. 1). The material obtained by synthesis at moderate alkaline condition (3M NaOH) shows an powder XRD pattern of a material with faujasite type structure. The analysis of the recorded d -values and the calculated unit cell parameter $a = 24.98 \text{ \AA}$ identifies the material as Na-X zeolite (Fig. 1a). In the case of synthesis with highly concentrated NaOH (6M NaOH), the formation of sodalite was recorded. The measured d -values correspond to those for hydroxyl-sodalite (reference card 76-1639 from PDF-2, Hassan *et al.*, 1983) (Fig. 1b). Under the same conditions, but with the addition of NaCl, chlorine-sodalite (reference card 88-2087, Beagley *et al.*, 1982) is formed (Fig. 1b). The measured d -values of the products obtained from the experiments in-

volving the additives of nitrate and sulfate salt correspond to those of the mineral cancrinite (Fig. 1c). In the PDF-2 database of the International Crystallographic Diffraction Data (ICDD), only reference cards of hydroxyl-cancrinite (46-1457, Khomyakov *et al.*, 1992) and carbonate-cancrinite (72-2076, Smolin *et al.*, 1981) are present. According to the d -values, the obtained products have the parameters of carbonate-cancrinite rather than hydroxyl-cancrinite. The product obtained from the nitrate salt shows d -values almost identical to the carbonate-cancrinite, which corresponds to the similar size and shape of the nitrate, and carbonate groups. The observed slight increase in d -values of the product obtained from sulfate salt may be due to both the larger size and

Fig. 1. Powder XRD pattern of starting materials: a) zeolite Na-X; b) sodalite-Cl and sodalite-OH; c) cancrinite- NO_3 and cancrinite- SO_4 ; d) comparison of the intensity of X-ray reflections of cancrinite- NO_3 and cancrinite- SO_4 .

different symmetry of the sulfate anion, and to the presence of OH-anions.

The relationship of X-ray reflection intensities of NO_3 -cancrinite corresponds to those of carbonate-cancrinite. The observed intensity of reflections of sulfate-cancrinite differs strongly from those of nitrate cancrinite (Fig. 1d), which is consistent with the different scattering ability of SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- anions.

The presence of the specific anions in the different forms of sodalite and cancrinite is confirmed by the results from FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 2). It should be noted that, in the spectrum of sodalite-Cl, along with band 1253 cm^{-1} assigned to Na-Cl bond (Peters and Noble, 2019), absorption bands associated with OH groups are observed (Fig. 2a), which suggests that this form is more correctly designated as sodalite-Cl,OH. According to the results, the cancrinite forms are mono-anionic (Fig. 2b).

Occlusion of ZnCl_2 in zeolite Na-X

The powder XRD pattern of the ZnCl_2 occluded in starting zeolite Na-X is characterized by a very high intensive background, low-intensity single broad lines corresponding to zeolite Na-X and sharp lines

of unreacted secondary crystallized ZnCl_2 (Fig. 3a). The recorded high intensive background and low-intensity lines of zeolite Na-X could be due to destruction of the faujasite structure by dissolution or the proceeding of occlusion. Normally, in the occlusion process, the occluding molecules (in this case ion pairs) occupy the free spaces without observed order. Therefore, in the present experiment, the occlusion of the heavy zinc and chloride ions in the structure is the reason for this almost X-ray amorphous character of the powder XRD pattern, because occluded ion pairs screen the interference of the secondary X-rays scattered by the zeolite Na-X framework. Such an influence of occluded ZnCl_2 in clinoptilolite structure has been described (Dimova *et al.*, 2009).

To clarify the reason that led to the observed X-ray amorphous character of the powder XRD pattern, an experiment of elution was conducted through washing of the occluded sample with distilled water. On the other hand, the elution results would give information about the stability and mobility of the occluded salt upon subsequent wetting.

After washing, the X-ray reflections of unreacted ZnCl_2 are not registered in the powder XRD pattern of the sample, and the zeolite Na-X reflections become significantly intense (Fig. 3a). This is

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of initial samples: a) sodalite-Cl and sodalite-OH; b) cancrinite- NO_3 and cancrinite- SO_4 .

Fig. 3. Powder XRD patterns of starting materials and their products after occlusion and elusion: a) Zeolite Na-X; b) Zn-exchanged Zeolite Na-X.

unequivocal evidence that the almost X-ray amorphous character of the powder XRD pattern of the occluded sample is due to a successful occlusion without destruction of the Na-X zeolite framework. However, the ratios of the X-ray reflection intensities of the eluted material differ from those of the starting zeolite Na-X (Fig. 3a). The preservation of the d -values suggests that only the exchange of extra-framework Na cations to Zn^{2+} takes place. To evaluate the influence of the ion exchange process on the occlusion process, occlusion experiments were performed on Zn-exchanged zeolite Na-X. The powder XRD pattern of Zn-exchanged zeolite Na-X occluded with excess $ZnCl_2$ (Fig. 3b) is similar to occluded zeolite Na-X (Fig. 3a) and corresponds to a completely X-ray amorphous material. The results of washing the occluded sample were also similar, with a recovery of the X-ray reflection intensities of the Zn exchanged Na-X zeolite (Fig. 3b). This result, as in the case of Na-X zeolite, shows that an occlusion process has taken place, in which there is no destruction of the framework.

The high degree of saturation with Zn^{2+} of the structure of zeolite Na-X in the occlusion process suggests the effective use of the occlusion products as materials with antibacterial properties. There

are many studies describing high antibacterial efficiency (95–100%) of Ag, Zn, Cu-exchanged zeolite forms for various microorganisms (*Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans*, and others; e.g., Zamzow and Schultze, 1995; Kirov and Terziiski, 1997; Kwakye-Awuah, 2008; Demirci *et al.*, 2014; Guerra *et al.*, 2015; Ferreira *et al.*, 2015). In the case of the occluded forms, Zn^{2+} in addition to being an ion-exchanged extra-framework cation is also present in significant amount as an occluded one. This fact, as well as the gradual and easy leaving the structure of the occluded ions, are a prerequisite for a significant increase in the antibacterial properties of the material.

Occlusion of KNO_3 in sodalite

The material obtained from the experiment of KNO_3 occlusion in sodalite-Cl shows preservation of the sodalite structure but with significant changes in the intensities of some reflections, especially at 310 and 321 (Fig. 4a). To determine the reason for the observed changes in intensities, the structure of sodalite was examined in more detail. According to the structural data (Hassan *et al.*, 2004), the extra-framework cations are located in the plain 310, and

Fig. 4. XRD data of starting sodalite-Cl,OH and its products after occlusion and elusion: a) obtained powder XRD patterns; b) fit between real and simulated 310, 222, and 321 reflections.

the anions are mainly located in the plain 321. The measured intensities in the simulated powder XRD pattern correspond very closely to the intensities of the powder X-ray data in reference card 88-2087 for pure chloric-sodalite. For this reason, the influence of different cations and anions on the intensity values of X-ray reflections was investigated using simulation of powder XRD patterns of samples with different composition by the PowderCell computer program. The intensity of planes 310 and 321 were monitored by comparing with intensity of 222, which is a reflection of the framework and is not affected by processes of ion exchange, occlusion, or hydration. For starting sodalite-Cl, the intensities of the three peaks 310, 222 and 321 slightly differ

from those in the simulated diffraction pattern of pure chloric-sodalite. Based on replacement of the type and number of cations and anions, the various intensities of 310 and 321 reflections were obtained. The best fit between the simulated and real powder XRD pattern is obtained when the cationic positions remain only sodium occupied, and in the anionic positions, in addition to chlorine anions, hydroxyl anions are placed (Fig. 4b). The resulting formula for the composition of the initial sample is $[\text{Na}_6\text{Al}_6\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{24}]\text{Na}_2\text{Cl}_{1.2}(\text{OH})_{0.8}$, which is also in agreement with the results of FTIR spectroscopy.

In the process of KNO_3 salt occlusion, cation-anion complexes are occluded. Since potassium nitrate was used in the experiment, *i.e.*, salt whose ions are

not present in the structure of the starting sodalite, exchange and occlusion of both cations and anions could occur. Simulations of powder XRD pattern of several different cation and anion sodalite compositions were made. A reliable good fit between the experimental and the calculated powder XRD pattern (Fig. 4b) was achieved for sodalite with composition:

The obtained formula shows that, during the experiment, there is no additional occlusion, but only ion exchange took place, which covers both the charge-balancing cations and the synthetically incorporated cation-anion pairs.

In order to establish the behavior of the exchanged ions, elution was carried out. The computer simulation of powder XRD pattern of the washed sample (Fig. 4b) gives the best fit between the real powder XRD pattern and the one calculated for the product composition:

The obtained result shows that, in the process of washing, the cation-anion pairs located in the chan-

nels of the sodalite structure come out, and water molecules take their place.

Occlusion of KNO_3 in cancrinite- SO_4

The results of the XRD analysis of the product of the interaction of cancrinite- SO_4 with a KNO_3 melt suggest preservation of the cancrinite structure, with significant changes in the intensities of the reflections of the planar networks in which the anions are mainly located (Fig. 5a). Applying the approach of powder XRD pattern simulation, cancrinite with a modified composition was obtained. It was found that a complete exchange of the SO_4^{2-} anion with NO_3 has taken place (Fig. 5b) and a partial change of the extra-framework cations. The X-ray-amorphous nature of the powder XRD pattern also suggests the occurrence of occlusion. The restoration of the intensities of the reflections in the powder XRD pattern of the washed sample (Fig. 5a) and a decrease in the intensity of the absorption bands of the NO_3 groups (Fig. 5b) unequivocally prove that, in addition to ion exchange, an occlusion process also took place in the cancrinite structure. The ratio of the intensities of the X-ray reflections suggests that, in the elution process, in addition to ion pairs

Fig. 5. Characterization of cancrinite- SO_4 and its products after occlusion and elusion: a) powder XRD patterns; b) FTIR spectra.

occluded during the interaction with KNO_3 melt, a part of those occluded during synthesis come out replaced by water molecules (Fig. 5).

CONCLUSIONS

A methodology for the occlusion of ZnCl_2 and KNO_3 in zeolites with a faujasite type structure and in the narrow-pored silicates sodalite and cancrinite has been developed and implemented. Peculiarities in powder XRD patterns have been established and interpreted, proving the progress of the occlusion process. Relationships of X-ray reflection intensities assessing the degree of occlusion and determining the composition of the occluded forms are derived. Possible applications of

the obtained materials modified by salt melt occlusion are suggested.

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